

SF1

Vaalan lukio

**Geoheritage and climate change opening
the secrets of home**

**Erasmus+-project week
Verbania, Italy, autumn 2016**

Visiting CERN - European organization for nuclear research. Geneva, Switzerland.

Universe of Particles
Universo de partículas →

Sightseeing in Geneva

Visiting the ethnographic museum.

Lunchbreak in Lausanne.

Arriving at Verbania.

Meeting the hostfamilies.

Welcome to Verbania!

I.I.S. Lorenzo Cobianchi, our partner school

Finnish students' presentations on Monday

- a municipality in northern Finland
- population: 3 063
- at first a part of the municipality of Säräisniemi (established in 1954)
- established in 1954
- area: 1 764,03km²
- the biggest employer: Pelso prison
- Economic structure:

Municipality hall

picture:
Jasmin
Väänänen

Italian students' presentations

Mikko Kiuttu, Rokua Geopark

Alessandra Magagna, Turin University

Ilaria Selva, Turin University

Days 3 & 4: Fieldtrip in the Sesia Valley

MAN and CLIMATE:
from the past, through the present, for the future

Italy, September 19th – September 23rd 2016 *Geoheritage and climate change opening the secrets of home*

Lunch in the school canteen

Teachers by Lake Maggiore

Visiting ARPA, the Regional Agency for the Protection of the environment

Presentation on dragonflies

to the

gonflies

d Europe

Presentation on diatoms

Visiting Rassa, an old village.

**Professor
Marco
Giardino,
Turin
University**

Edoardo Dellarole, director of Sesia Val Grande Geopark

Visiting the local museum

The cattle was taken back to the farm from the mountains.

Heading for the Walser Museum

A local farm in the mountains

Comune di Riva Valdobbia
**MUSEO ETNOGRAFICO DI STORIA E
TRADIZIONI WALSER (MUSEO RABERNAUDO)**

E' stato allestito negli anni 1990-1991 e ha sede in una costruzione eretta nel XVII secolo secondo i canoni dell'architettura vallesana. All'interno di dodici locali sono stati ricostruiti gli ambienti della tipica abitazione walsere: al piano terra la stalla, il soggiorno con la stufa in pietra ollare, la stanza per la lavorazione del latte e la dispensa; nei piani superiori le camere di abitazione e il fienile. Nel Museo sono esposti, oltre ad un interessante serie di attrezzi da lavoro che testimoniano le attività praticate per secoli dalle popolazioni locali, alcuni costumi tradizionali maschili e femminili. Preziosa testimonianza storica della vita walsere è una raccolta di pergamene quattrocentesche e cinquecentesche riguardanti le famiglie del luogo.

DAL RISO AL ROSA
www.dalrisoalrosa.it

Sentieri dell'Arte
Via Vigna - Alta Via dei Walser
Oratorio di Sant'Antonio
1700
La facciata, intonacata in bianco, è un esempio di arte barocca vallesana. L'oratorio è stato costruito nel 1700, in occasione della festa di Sant'Antonio, patrono della valle. L'edificio è stato restaurato nel 1980, mantenendo l'aspetto originale. L'interno è decorato con stucchi e affreschi. L'oratorio è aperto al pubblico durante le festività di Sant'Antonio, che si celebrano dal 15 al 23 giugno.

The Walser Museum

SI PREGA DI
NON TOCCARE
GRAZIE

La Minéra Hostel in Alagna Valsesia

Waiting for the cable car

Heading for Monte Rosa and the Mosso Institute

Passo dei Salati

Monte Rosa

Activities and field work on Monte Rosa

5

Ateneja

Fam. Boraginaceae
***Eritrichium nanum* (A.L.) Tenore - ERITRICHIO NANO**

L'specie tipica delle alte alpi, dove si
 trova tra 2500 e 3000 metri, in Valais
 e presente su Monte Rosa, Corone
 e Camoscio. Cresce su rupi e
 facimenti con roccia affiorante.
 Il foglio è ovale, appuntito e
 la pianta è lanuginosa.

Weather Station on Monte Rosa

The highlight of the project week

The Mosso Institute

1846

1910

PER GLI STUDI SEVERI
PER L' ESPERIMENTO SAGACE
PER LA PACE E LA VITA
NELLA MAESTA' DELLE ALPI
ANGELO MOSSO
CREAVA E DONAVA
QUESTA SERENA DIMORA
AI SUOI ALLIEVI
A QUELLI CHE ANCORA
NON ERANO

Bilancia analitica di precisione
Officina S. Giorgio, Torino

Quarzite

Gneiss aplítico

Quarzo

Activities in groups

Visiting the Botanical Garden in Verbania

What a wonderful week!

**Preparing presentations for the
farewell party.**

Students' presentations

Climate strongly conditioned migrations of Walser population in the first millenium and in the middleage they colonized the high quota areas in our territories establishing an autonomous economy based on agriculture and breeding.

After the «small glaciation» (about 1500 a.C.) climate didn't allow to do Walser activities and gradually brought to another migration flow to foreign countries with the consequent abandonment of some alps and villages.

IC Istituto L. COBIANCHI
Università del Piemonte Orientale

Erasmus+

Andrea Bonisoli, Guglielmo Zanetti Chesi, Taha Atili,
Romani, Olli Mänttä, Eeva Karppinen

**The farewell party on Friday evening at school.
Greetings from the school authorities and the
principal.**

The whole Erasmus+-team of the teachers

The teachers' official dinner

See you in Vaala in May 2017.

Photos

Vaalan lukio

Jouni Kauhanen

Riitta Olsbo

Jani Raitanen

**Vaalan lukiolaisia Euroscola-matkalla
Strasbourgissa 11.10.-13.10.2017**

Euroscola-matkalle osallistuneet opiskelijat. Niko puuttuu kuvasta.

Syksyn aikana valmistauduttiin Euroscola-päivään

Kokoonnuimme useampaan kertaan koulupäivän jälkeen

Frankfurtissa menomatalla 11.10.2017

Odottelemassa metrokyytiä kaupungin keskusta

**Oppaanamme oli vaalalaissyntyinen Eila
Denning**

Frankfurtin tuomiokirkko

Lounaalla italialaisessa ravintolassa

Frankfurtin kattojen yllä

**Frankfurtin kaupungintalo Vanhassa
kaupungissa**

Frankfurtin Vanha kaupunkia Römerin

**Vierailimme Historiallisessa
museossa**

Pienoismalli Frankfurtista

Torstai 12.10.2017 Strasbourgissa Ranskassa

Matkalla Europarlamenttiin

Jännittävä päivä edessä

**Louise Weiss-rakennuksen
sisäpiha**

Päivän ohjeet ja ryhmiin

EU-lippu

EU:n 28 jäsenmaan liput

Europarlamentin istuntosali 12.10.2017

EUROSCOLA DU 12 OCTOBRE 2017
PARLEMENT EUROPÉEN À STRASBOURG

Opiskelijoita ja opettajia 24 eri maasta

Euroscola-päivä oli tarkoitettu ns. EPAS-projektiin osallistuville kouluille.

Petriina ja Silja odottavat tyynesti vuoroaan

Petriina ja Silja esittelevät Suomea, Vaalaa ja Vaalan lukiota

Ilona ja Aino-Maija kuuntelevat tarkkaavaisina keskustelua

**Mahdollisia tulevia europarlamentaarikkoja
lukiostamme**

Olli-Pekka pyytää puheenvuoroa

Mukava ja ikimuistettava päivä

**EUROSCOLA DU 12 OCTOBRE 2017
PARLEMENT EUROPÉEN À STRASBOURG**

Opettajien virallinen valokuva; Riitta ja Jouni keskellä

**Strasbourgissa
13.10.2017**

Lähdössä tutustumaan Strasbourgin nähtävyyksiin

Ill-joki

**Strasbourgjin tori Vanhassa kaupungissa;
kuvassa kaupungin vanhin rakennus**

Strasbourg katedraali

Astronominen kello

Strasbourg katedraalin katolta kuvattuna

Vierailimme myös Notre Dame-museossa

Opiskelijoilla oli tehtävänä kuvata yksi kiinnostava kohde ja esitellä se myöhemmin muille blogissamme.

Lounaalla kiinalaisessa ravintolassa

Hotellihuoneiden luovutus. Kotimatka alkaa.

Kuvat

Euroscola

Riitta Olsbo

Jouni Kauhanen

**Tutustu myös blogiimme
osoitteessa**

<https://euroscolavaala.wordpress.com/>

SF2

CLIMATE CHANGE AND GLACIERS - ACTIVITY A

Comparison of multitemporal orthophotos (years 1989, 1994, 1999, 2007, 2010, 2012) for understanding changes in the glacial environment of the Ban Glacier (Lepontine Alps, Arbola Group, Formazza Valley, Piemonte Region)

1. Observe and analyze each photo.
2. What are the two main geomorphological elements of this alpine environment?
3. Compare similarities and differences of the environment in different years.
4. Track the changes of the two main geomorphological elements through time by using different colors on the millimeter transparent paper.
5. Estimate the areal variations of Ban Glacier and lake through time.
6. Estimate the total length of the glacier through time by comparing the position of the glacier front.
7. Interpret what are the ongoing phenomena and write a short statement for describing them.

CLIMATE CHANGE AND GLACIERS - ACTIVITY B

Identification of glacial lakes through space and time (Valaisan Glacier, Graian Alps, Rutor-Valaisan Group, Aosta Valley; Google Earth satellite image, 2009)

1. Observe the satellite image and identify glacial lakes.
2. Indicate and interpret the possible sequence of formation of glacial lakes (Which are the oldest and which the most recent? Why did they formed through different times?).
3. What is the reason for different colors of the water into the lakes?
4. Write a short statement for describing the above-mentioned phenomena.

CLIMATE CHANGE AND GLACIERS - ACTIVITY C

Identification of changes through time of the Albaron di Sea Glacier (Graian Alps, Ciamarella Group, Grande di Lanzo Valley, Piemonte Region) and inventories of glaciers in Italy.

1. Observe and compare the photographs of the Albaron di Sea Glacier taken in years 1904 and 2007, as well as the ortophoto taken in years 1988 and 2012.
2. Look at the following table and at the graph.
3. What is the relationship between the number of glaciers, the percentage area loss and the glacier size?
4. What is the ongoing phenomenon? What are the effects of this phenomenon on a glacier over the next few years?

Data from inventories of glaciers in Italy		
year of the inventory	number of glaciers	total glacierized area
1927	774	n.d.
1960	838	500 km ²
1989	787	470 km ²
2015	903	370 km ²

Non-linear relationship between percentage area loss from CGI Inventory (1960) to the New Inventory (2015; y axis) and glacier size (x axis). (From: Il Nuovo Catasto dei Ghiacciai Italiani, 2015).

These activities were realized in cooperation with Cristina Viani PhD, Department of Earth Sciences, University of Torino, and the Italian Glaciological Committee

CLIMATE CHANGE AND GLACIERS - ACTIVITY D

Identification of changes through time of the Lys Glacier (Pennine Alps, Monte Rosa Group, Lys Valley, Aosta Valley).

1. Observe and compare the photographs taken in years 1868 and 2011 of the Lys Glacier.
2. Find recognizable landforms and other features to be used as equivalent points to be used as references for photographic comparisons.
3. Use the map on ortophoto for identifying the glacial extents related to the photographs taken in years 1868 and 2011. Complete related labels and legend on the map, avoiding those not related to the presented data.
4. What is the ongoing phenomenon? Indicate some relevant geomorphic processes and factors related to the environmental changes.

ACTIVITY D - LYS GLACIER
(Pennine Alps, Monte Rosa Group, Lys Valley, Aosta Valley)

